

The Impact of Traffic Safety Education Program among the Tricycle Drivers in the Municipality of Cabagan, Isabela

Rodel L. Asuncion, PhD.

Associate Professor I, College of Criminal Justice Education,
Isabela State University, Cabagan, Isabela Philippines

Abstract:- This study used the impact assessment framework to evaluate the outcomes of an extension program for TODA members at the Xentro Mall in Anao, Cabagan, Isabela, in August 2017 called "THE IMPACT OF A TRAFFIC SAFETY EDUCATION PROGRAM AMONG THE TRICYCLE DRIVERS IN THE MUNICIPALITY OF CABAGAN, ISABELA". Inputs, Activities, Outputs, Outcomes, and Impact were the main factors that were identified and measured during the evaluation. According to the study's conclusions, the beneficiaries of the TSE program activities carried out by the CCJE were discovered to have identified the suggested inputs, outputs, and project implementation activities as being undertaken by the beneficiaries. The training's medium-term impacts revealed that the beneficiaries understanding of traffic rules and regulations, traffic signs, and road courtesy and defensive driving had improved. As to the long-term impacts of the extension program, all the beneficiaries who participated in the survey said that they did not violate any traffic rules, they realized the importance of their occupation, they became more careful while traversing the public thoroughfare, and they maintained good relationships with their fellow TODA members and their passengers. Moreover, the beneficiaries who participated in the survey also mentioned that the local government unit of Cabagan, Isabela, showed their full support during the implementation of the program, representatives from the Philippine National Police, the Land Transportation Office, and faculty members from the College of Criminal Justice Education served as lecturers during the training, pre-tests and post-tests were administered before and after the training, and aside from lectures, the beneficiaries also agreed that during the training, they participated in demonstration exercises. Among the 16 participants during the survey, 7 of them agreed that due to scheduling conflicts, some beneficiaries did not complete the program, 3 of them said that the site of the training is too far, and other participants in the training were not focused on the topics. There were 2 participants who agreed during the survey that the time allotted for the training is not sufficient. Finally, the 16 participants during the survey agreed that after the training, they fully comprehended their role, responsibilities, significance of their

occupation, and they also improved their services to their passengers.

Keywords:- Traffic Safety Education (TSE), Tricycle Operators and Drivers Association (TODA), Beneficiaries, Impacts

I. INTRODUCTION

By acting as a link between academic institutions and society, extension programs are essential to higher education. By providing educational opportunities and services outside of the campus, these initiatives seek to share the university's knowledge and skills with the local community.

Extension Programs/Projects/Activities are meant to provide support to marginalized communities in the form of various development interventions to alleviate challenging situations experienced by people living in these communities. Challenges come in different forms, like unemployment, underemployment, illiteracy, malnutrition, unsafe and hazardous living conditions, etc. These challenges are manifestations of the poverty experienced by the majority of people living in communities that are being served by the Isabela State University Cabagan (ISUC) campus.

The College of Criminal Justice Education (CCJE) at Cabagan, Isabela is committed to the fulfillment of the extension agenda of the university, most especially in peace and order and public safety. One of the extension programs conducted by the college is the TSE for TODA. The participants of the extension program were the TODA members at Xentro Mall, Anao, Cabagan, Isabela and it was conducted in August 2017.

The college conducted the extension project because based on the result of the benchmarked and needs assessment conducted, some TODA members are not familiar with the traffic laws and ordinances being implemented in the Municipality. Furthermore, another reason why the college conducted the project, based on the available record of the Philippine National Police, Cabagan Police Station, involvement of tricycle drivers in vehicular traffic-related accidents in the municipality from Calendar Year 2015 up to Calendar Year 2017 is very high.

Fig. 1: Involvement of tricycle drivers in vehicular traffic related accidents from C.Y. 2015 up to 2021.

Source: PNP Cabagan, Investigation Section

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Generally, this study aimed to assess the extension project entitled “THE IMPACT OF A TRAFFIC SAFETY EDUCATION PROGRAM AMONG THE TRICYCLE DRIVERS IN THE MUNICIPALITY OF CABAGAN, ISABELA”.

Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

- Draw a profile of the extension program beneficiaries.
- Assess the program in terms of:
 - ✓ inputs, resources or support extended to the intended beneficiaries or used to implement the project
 - ✓ activities, actions taken or works conducted
 - ✓ outputs, goods, products, services as a result of the development intervention undertaken
 - ✓ outcomes, short or medium-term effects of the intervention
 - ✓ impact, positive and negative/primary and secondary long-term effects of the development intervention.
- Identify and describe best practices in the conduct of the program that brought about positive effects to intended beneficiaries.
- Identify and describe loopholes that were experienced during project implementation that brought about negative effects to intended beneficiaries.
- Determine lessons learned from the experiences of project implementers, collaborators, and beneficiaries.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study falls under the sphere of evaluation research which has a strong focus on the results of development activities on their intended beneficiaries (OEDKE-The World Bank, 2004). The study employed quantitative research processes specifically survey and small-scale rapid assessment and participatory appraisals. These methods are aimed at estimating the impacts of on intended beneficiaries. The Rapid Assessment Ex-Post Impact Evaluation is one of the four models of impact evaluation (OEDKE-The World Bank, 2004). Data for the study were obtained from a combined method of survey, group interviews, and available secondary data. Data analysis used in this study is based on the grounded theory orientation in terms of coding and development of themes in a constant comparative analytic process (Glasser & Strauss, 2006). Basic quantitative data analysis like frequency counts, mean and percentages were also used.

Using the framework shown in Figure 2, this study sought to assess the effects of the extension program for road safety conducted by the College of Criminal Justice Education in August 2017. The inputs, actions, outputs, results, and effect were the main factors that were identified and measured during the assessment.

Fig. 2: Impact Assessment Framework

The study leader crafted the instrument used in the evaluation of the extension program. Other tasks were the identification of data sources, respondents who answered the survey questionnaires, key informant interviews, focused group discussions, and secondary data collection.

Data collection and analysis, and writing the final output of the project carried out in a manner that the

proponent/implementor of the extension project under evaluation was not evaluated his/her own project. After the finalization of the analysis and write-up, each study leader reviewed the output of the team member who evaluated the project. Validation procedures carried out for questions arise during the reporting of results of the study among the members of the research team.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study presents the analysis and interpretation of the data gathered following the order of the study objectives.

- **What are the profiles of the beneficiaries in terms of:**

A. Age bracket of the beneficiaries

Fig. 3: Age of the beneficiaries

As shown in Figure 3, 25% of the total numbers of beneficiaries were under the age bracket of 38-42, followed by 19% for age brackets 28-32, 33-37, and 43-47, while

12% were under the age bracket of 48-52, and there were only 6% under the age bracket of 54 above.

B. Civil Status

Fig. 4: Civil Status of the beneficiaries

As presented in Figure 4, 88% of the beneficiaries were married, while single and separated beneficiaries have the same percentage, which are 6.25%.

C. Educational Attainment

Fig. 5: Educational Attainment

As shown in Figure 5, the distribution of beneficiaries according to educational attainment, 25% of beneficiaries were high school graduates, while high school level, college

level, and vocational school graduates had the same percentage of 18.75%, and only 12.5% of total numbers of beneficiaries were elementary level.

D. Sex

Fig. 6: Distribution of beneficiaries according to sex

Figure 6 shows the distribution of beneficiaries according to sex. All beneficiaries were male, with an equivalent percentage of 100.

E. Number of years in the occupation

Fig. 7: Number of years in the occupation

Figure 7 depicts the distribution of beneficiaries based on the number of years worked in each occupation. Out of the 16 beneficiaries, 56.25% are in the year bracket 6–10,

followed by 25% in the year bracket 11–15, and 6.25% in the year brackets 1–5, 16–20, and 21–25.

F. Other source of income of the beneficiaries

Fig. 8: Other source of income

Figure 8 reveals that 81.25% had no other source of income, while only 6.25% had another source of income such as being a vendor, farmer, and barangay kagawad.

G. Monthly income of the beneficiaries

Fig. 9: Monthly income of the beneficiaries

Figure 9 shows that 56.25% of all beneficiaries had an average monthly income of 1,000–3,000, 31.25% had an average monthly income of 4,000–6,000, and only 6.25%

had an average monthly income of 10,000-12,000 and 13,000–15,000.

H. Number of family members with income

Fig. 10: Number of family members with income

Figure 10 revealed that 31.25% had four income-earning family members, 25% had one to two income-

earning family members, and only 18.75% had three income-earning family members.

I. Monthly income of the households

Table 11: Monthly income of the household

Figure 11 depicts the distribution of beneficiaries based on the household's monthly income. The household income bracket of 1,000-5,000 accounts for 62.5% of the total number of beneficiaries, followed by 18.75% of the

household income bracket of 11,000-15,000, 12.5% of the household income bracket of 21,000 and above, and only 6.25% of the household income bracket of 6,000-10,000.

V. ASSESSMENT OF THE PROGRAM IN TERMS OF

A. Inputs, resources, or support extended to the beneficiaries

Table 1: Inputs, activities and outputs

Indicators	Frequency	Percentage
1. Free meals and snacks during the training	16	100
2. Writing materials and copies of the topics are free	16	100
3. Training area is comfortable and organized	16	100
4. Municipal traffic ordinances was discussed during the training	16	100
5. Traffic scheme and penalties was discussed during the training	16	100
6. Traffic control and signages was discussed during the training	16	100
7. Defensive driving techniques was discussed during the training	16	100

As appeared in Table 1, all proposed indicators for inputs, resources, and services were identified by the beneficiaries as activities and services conducted during the implementation of the project on TSE for TODA members in August 2017.

One of the most critical elements of traffic management is traffic education. This pillar's goal is to teach

road users, such as tricycle drivers, about traffic rules and regulations, traffic ordinances, and safe riding skills. According to Hintural L. A. Jr. et al. (2016), the traffic education department may create programs like holding discussions or symposiums, or creating advertisements on current data on traffic and vehicle accidents to inform the public about the current state of the roads.

B. Outcomes, short or medium-term effects of the intervention

Indicators	Frequency	Percentage
1. My understanding of traffic regulations and ordinances has improved.	16	100
2. As a tricycle driver, my courtesy has improved.	15	93.75
3. I learned how to become a defensive driver in order to avoid a road accident.	16	100
4. My understanding of the different types of traffic signs has improved.	16	100

Table 2: The projects' medium-term impacts on the beneficiaries

Table 2 shows that indicators 1, 3 and 4 had the highest percentage, which is 100%, while indicator number 2 is 93.75%. According to Valdueza (2013), education in traffic safety can be done on three different levels: (1) teaching traffic safety knowledge, which emphasizes the importance of safety training and education; (2) practicing

and training traffic safety knowledge in its actual application, which deals with the practical aspects of safety education and teaches one how to move about in a safe manner; and (3) developing safety morality, which teaches one how to act in a safe manner.

C. Impact/Long term effects of the training conducted

Table 3: The projects' long-term impacts on the beneficiaries

Indicators	Frequency	Percentage
1. Following the training, the number of my regular passengers increased.	14	87.5
2. After attending the program, my income as a tricycle driver improved.	12	75
3. After I attended the training, I did not break any traffic laws or ordinances.	16	100
4. I learned to value my occupation after attending the training.	16	100
5. I learned how to drive more safely after attending the training.	16	100
6. I was able to maintain good relationships with my colleagues and passengers.	16	100

As shown in Table 3, indicators 3, 4, 5, and 6 had the highest percentage, which is 100%, followed by indicator 1 with 87.5% and only 75% for indicator 2. Andinyan J.B. (2020) emphasized the significance of tricycle drivers in the

daily lives of passengers. They are a common form of transportation for commuters and vacationers. To avoid or reduce the risk of road traffic accidents caused by them, it is crucial that they comprehend traffic rules and regulations.

VI. BEST PRACTICES IN THE CONDUCT OF THE PROGRAM THAT BROUGHT ABOUT POSITIVE EFFECTS TO THE BENEFICIARIES.

Table 4: Best practices

Best Practices	Frequency	Percentage
1. The training was supported by the local government of Cabagan, Isabela.	16	100
2. ISU, CCJE, the Philippine National Police's traffic enforcement unit, and the Land Transportation Office are among the lecturers (LTO).	16	100
3. Before (Pre-test) and after (Post-test) the training, there is a test.	16	100
4. Aside from the lectures, we participated in demonstration exercises where we learnt how to drive tricycles.	15	93.75

According to Table 4, best practice number 4 had a frequency of 15, or 93.75%, whereas best practice numbers 1, 2, and 3 had the highest frequency, with an equivalent percentage of 100. Seva R.R. (2017) underlined that the government can explore laws on ongoing instruction in MC handling and safe driving practices for drivers. Aydinan J.B. (2020) proposed in his study that proper road safety education be carried out for the welfare of the general public, and that state universities and colleges be utilized to

give such programs for the members of the Tricycle Operators and Drivers Association (TODA). In order to lower the risks of accidents on the road, these drivers must be instructed in the proper methods, plans, or tactics. The tricycle drivers will benefit from this since it would allow them to brush up on their understanding of traffic laws and regulations. The knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors of drivers regarding traffic laws and regulations must be prioritized by the government.

VII. LOOPHOLES THAT WERE EXPERIENCED DURING PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION THAT BROUGHT ABOUT NEGATIVE EFFECTS TO THE BENEFICIARIES.

Table 5: Problems encountered

Problems/Constraints/Loopholes Encountered	Frequency	Percentage
1. The time allotted for the training is not sufficient	2	12.5
2. Due to scheduling conflicts, some beneficiaries did not complete the program.	7	43.75
3. The site of the training is too far away from our TODA.	3	18.75
4. Other participants in the training were unfamiliar with traffic laws.	2	12.5
5. The other participants in the training were not focused on the topics.	3	18.75

As shown in Table 5, the most common problem encountered by the beneficiaries during the TSE program is item number 2, which has a frequency of 7, or an equivalent percentage of 43.75, followed by items 3 and 5 with an equivalent percentage of 18.75, and items 1 and 4 with a frequency of 2, or an equivalent percentage of 12.5. According to Sermona N.D. et al. (2020), one of the factors affecting the implementation of the extension program, the

respondents still see the schedule as a concern. Even when the schedules were already set in the proposals and in the memoranda of agreement, other activities would sometimes come up for both parties. In some instances, only a few participants will attend the activities. Moreover, the faculty members also expressed that transportation has been a challenge, especially in hard-to-reach communities.

VIII. LESSONS LEARNED FROM THE EXPERIENCES OF PROJECT BENEFICIARIES

Table 6: Lessons learned

Lessons Learned from Experiences	Frequency	Percentage
1. After the training, I fully comprehended the role and significance of my occupation as a tricycle driver.	16	100
2. I learned how to be a responsible tricycle driver after the training.	16	100
3. I learned and improved my service to my passengers.	16	100

Table 6 shows that the beneficiaries identified all of the recommended indicators as lessons learned during the implementation of the TSE program. According to Aydinan J.B (2020), it is essential that tricycle drivers are knowledgeable about the road traffic rules and regulations, but it is much more desirable if they are compliant.

IX. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, it has been realized that majority of the beneficiaries were under the age bracket of 38-42, majority of them were married and high school graduates. All beneficiaries were males and as to the number of years in the occupation, 56.25% of them have been worked 6-10 years as TODA members or tricycle drivers. Majority of the beneficiaries had no other source of income aside from members of the TODA. As to the monthly income of the beneficiaries, 56.25% have a monthly income of 1,000-3,000; more than 4 members of the family of the beneficiaries have monthly income and the total monthly income of the family members is ranging to 1,000 – 5,000.

Further, all of the recommended inputs, outputs, and activities conducted during the implementation of the project were carried out by the CCJE. The training's medium-term impacts revealed that the understanding of the beneficiaries on the traffic rules, ordinances and different traffic signs have improved and they also became defensive driver. As to the long-term effect of the training, the involved beneficiaries during the survey said that they did

not violate any traffic rules after they attended the training; they understood the value of their occupation; they drove more safely; and they maintained a good relationship with their passengers and their fellow TODA members. As to the best practices, the involved beneficiaries during the survey said that the local government of Cabagan, Isabela, supported the TSE program of the CCJE, faculty members of the CCJE, the Philippine National Police, and the Land Transportation Office in Cabagan, Isabela, served as lecturers, and the facilitators administered pre-tests before the commencement of the TSE program and post-tests after the implementation of the program. Conflict of schedules, accessibility of the training site, and beneficiaries' concentrations during the implementation of the TSE program were the problems identified by the beneficiaries involved during the survey. Lastly, the lessons learned from the experiences of project beneficiaries said that they fully understood the significance of their occupation as tricycle drivers, and after the training, they became more responsible in conveying their passengers. In light of the conclusions, the following were recommended: First, conduct another set of training and encourage all tricycle drivers operating in the urbanized barangay of Cabagan, Isabela, to join. Second, the training plan will be suited to the beneficiaries' availability. Third, the venue of the training is accessible to the identified beneficiaries.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Implementation of Extension Services in Select State Universities and Colleges in the Philippines.
By: NievaLouwah D. Sermona et al 2020.
- [2.] Traffic Safety Education the Missing Link in Traffic Safety.
By: Donal M. English 2011
- [3.] Knowledge and Level of Compliance of Tricycle Drivers on Traffic Rules and Regulation: A Case of the Tricycle City of the Philippines
By: Januaryn Jose B. Aydinan 2020
- [4.] Traffic Education Awareness Among Tricycle Drivers in Buenavista, Agusan Del Norte, Philippines
By: Nelson R. Arceo Jr. et al 2019
- [5.] Modeling Motorcycle Accident Severity in the Philippines Using Helmet Use, Riding Experience, and Driving Behaviour
By: Rosemary R. Seva 2017.